

PALMEIRAS' PROBABILISTIC ADVANTAGES OF WINNING A MATCH WHEN PLAYING AT HOME IN THE 2022 BRASILEIRÃO CHAMPIONSHIP

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Abstract

Soccer is a popular sport, attracting interest in the betting business. Soccer score prediction and statistical thinking have been documented since the 1970s. This study aims to understand soccer and mathematics to understand teams' advantages and disadvantages. The study aims to validate the probabilities of obtaining the best result in matches played at home in the 2022 Brasileirão. Mathematical tools like binomial distribution, Poisson distribution, Bernoulli, and variance are used to calculate probabilities. The article is organized with explanations of formulas and application of these tools. The research shows that Palmeiras performs better at home compared to away games, indicating numerous advantages. However, the analysis is partially limited due to the use of formulas that lack a proper global model. Despite these limitations, the research provides credibility to soccer and is practical for students and others interested in the application of mathematics.

Keywords: Palmeiras, Brasileirão, Statistics, Probability.

1. Introduction

Soccer is a world-renowned sport and therefore attracts interest in the betting business. It has gained notoriety in recent years and attracts various types of fans, such as experienced analysts, club managers, and others (Rahman et al., 2018). There are bets for the various factors involving a soccer match, such as, of course, the result. Soccer score prediction and statistical thinking in sports have been documented since early work in the 1970s (Carpita et al. 2015). There are several ways to try to predict the outcome of a soccer game, such as statistics. Generally, an encouraging crowd generates support for the team playing, and they are more present when a team plays at home.

It is in this sense that the interest to carry out this investigation arose. Through this study, I will be able to understand more about two subjects that I do not understand so well, soccer and mathematics. I intend to use the knowledge acquired to understand the teams' advantages and disadvantages mathematically.

Thus, this work aims to validate within the condition of playing at home, the probabilities of obtaining the best result. More specifically, this paper aims to answer "To what extent did Palmeiras have probabilistic advantages when winning in matches played at home in the 2022 Brasileirão?". To obtain this answer, mathematical tools were used with the binomial distribution such as the approximation of

the normal, Poisson distribution, Bernoulli and the variance. The article is organized with explanations of the formulas that will be used, in sequence the application of such tools to calculate the probabilities.

$$\binom{n}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-k}$$

Where,

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$$

2. Binomial Distribution

To understand some formulas and symbols, we need to state and recap some definitions.

- **VARIABLE X:** The variable X is a number of something that is related to success in n repetitions with a given probability.
- **MEAN/EXPECTED VALUE/HOPE:** E is the expected value or hope of X .

$$\mu = E(X) = n \times p$$

In counting problems, the binomial distribution naturally arises. Variables such as the number of crowns in n tosses of an honest coin among others are variables that under certain conditions can be represented by a binomial distribution.

When performing independent repetitions of an experiment where the only interest is in a dichotomy (success or failure), we are dealing with a given dataset in which a binomial random variable can be defined. The binomial distribution can be used as long as the experimental conditions remain constant and the probability of event A remains constant (Meyer, 2010).

Consider n independent repetitions of a random experiment, where the probability of success is $P(A) = p$, and the probability of failure is $P(x) = 1 - p$. Thus, X =number of occurrences of event A which is referred to as a binomial random variable with n and p parameters.

The notation $X \sim B(n, p)$ denotes that the random variable X has a binomial distribution with n and p parameters. Thus, the probability of exactly k successes in a series of n independent trials with p probability of success corresponds to:

3. Variance and Standard Deviation

$$\sigma^2 = Var(X) = n \times p \times (1 - p),$$

The standard deviation (SD), is the square root of the variance, thus:

$$\sigma = DP(X) = \sqrt{n \times p \times (1 - p)}.$$

4. Normal Approximation of the Binomial Distribution with Continuity Correction

The Binomial and Normal probability distributions are two of the most commonly used to represent discrete and continuous random variable data, respectively. Meyer (2010) claims that the relationship between the binomial and normal distributions stems from the DeMoivre-Laplace approximation, which states that under certain conditions, the normal distribution can be used as an approximation of the binomial distribution. Thus, if X has a binomial distribution with n and p parameters, and if

$$Z = \frac{X - np}{\sqrt{np(1-p)}},$$

then for large n , Z will have a distribution approximately $N(0, 1)$. Through an approximation made with the help of Stirling's formula, it is found that under the above conditions, if Y is the representation of the normal distribution coming from the distribution Z when $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then for large n , Z has a distribution of approximately $N(0, 1)$, in the sense that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(Z \leq z) = P(Y \leq z).$$

The distribution of the discrete variable (Z) approximates the distribution of the continuous variable by using the normal approximation to the binomial distribution (Y). As a result, continuity corrections were used

$$P(X = x) \approx P(x - \frac{1}{2} \leq Y \leq x + \frac{1}{2}).$$

5. Bernoulli

A random experiment with only two possible outcomes, true or false, and whose success probability remains constant throughout the experiment.

Bernoulli's random variable (X) has only two possible values. 1 if success (S) occurs and 0 if failure (F), with success probability p , that is,

x	0	1
$P(x)=X$	1-p	p

If $X \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p)$ it can be shown that: $E(X) = p$ and $Var(X) = p(1 - p)$

The Binomial model is formed by independent repetitions of a Bernoulli trial with the same probability of "success" occurrence. As a result, the probability function for the random variable X with Bernoulli distribution is:

$$P(X = x) = p^x(1 - p)^{1-x}, x = 0, 1.$$

6. Binomial and Poisson Distribution

Let λ be the average number of events in a variable interval such as time and volume, or the average rate of occurrence per unit measured. Let the random variable X be the count of the number of events occurring in the interval. Then under certain conditions it can be shown that,

$$V(X) = \lambda$$

The Poisson distribution is related to experiments in which an event occurs at some time, area, volume, or other interval. It is a probabilistic model that can account for a wide range of observable phenomena. When the number of possible discrete occurrences is much greater than the average number of occurrences in a given time or space interval, the Poisson distribution is applicable.

The outcomes must occur at random, that is, entirely by chance, and the probability of occurrence must not be affected by whether or not the outcomes have previously occurred, ensuring that the occurrences are independent. The Poisson distribution is a limiting case of the binomial distribution that arises when the number of trials n grows indefinitely while the product np , which is the expected value of the number of trials' successes, remains constant.

Considering the equation of the binomial distribution, by admitting $n \rightarrow \infty$, $p \rightarrow 0$, $np = \alpha$ (constant). Thus, the Poisson distribution with parameter α :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(X = x) = \frac{e^{-\alpha} \alpha^x}{x!}$$

Thus, one can use an approximation of the binomial properties with the Poisson distribution probabilities, when n is large and p is small.

7. Explicação do Brasileirão

The "Campeonato Brasileiro de Futebol da série A", known as the Brasileirão, is an annual competition between 20 national teams in Brazil. During the course of the season, each team plays twice against the same opponent, once in its home stadium and once in the opponent's stadium, with a total of 38 games per team. It applies a point system, where a win is worth three points, a draw one point, and no points are awarded for losses. The team with the most points accumulated at the end is the champion. Since the beginning of the Brazilian Championship in 1959, Palmeiras has had the most wins with 11 titles until 2022. The team has won several matches,

maintaining the character of previous years by winning most of the matches at home. In 2022 there were 13 home wins and 10 away wins, corresponding to 68% and 52% of the matches, respectively (Table 1). Thus, due to its broad relevance, it was decided to investigate it.

Table 1. Results of Palmeiras' games at home and away.

CONDITION	WIN	DRAW	LOSE
IN THE HOUSE	13	4	2
OUTSIDE THE HOUSE	10	8	1

8. Palmeiras Playing at Home

As already stated, the condition of playing at home significantly influences the course of the game,

because the fans transmit a motivating energy to the players. As already stated before, the mathematical tools related to the binomial distribution were used to calculate to what extent the condition of playing at home influenced the results of Palmeiras' 2022 matches.

Let X be a random variable representing the number of home wins for Palmeiras in n matches, with constant probability p . Based on the data for 2022, we assume that the probability of this team winning at home is $p = 0.68$, and of not winning (losses + draws) is $(1 - p) = 0.32$. Thus, the probability distribution associated with the random variable X , by the binomial distribution formula, is binomial with parameters $n = 19$ and $p = 0.68$ represented in Table 2.

Table 2. Random variable probability distribution $X \sim B(19; 0.68)$.

X	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$P(X = X)$	3.96^{-10}	1.6^{-8}	3.058^{-7}	3.68^{-6}	3.13^{-5}	1.99^{-4}	9.91^{-4}	0.0039	0.0124	0.0323

X	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
$P(X = X)$	0.0687	0.119	0.169	0.194	0.176	0.125	0.0664	0.0249	5.88^{-3}	6.57^{-4}

This probability distribution is also represented binomially in Graph 1 and normally in Graph 2, a bell curve. A bell curve is a graph that depicts a normal distribution of data; this typically indicates that the variables were within normal expectations and behaved predictably. The overall probability is represented by the graph's area. The mean groups the probabilistic values and can be greater than zero. The standard deviation is depicted on the graph by the

edges of the graph, where the curve is concentrated or dispersed away from typical, expected values.

Graph 1. Probability function graph of the random variable $X \sim B(19; 0.68)$.

Graph 2. Bell curve of Graph 1.

When you compare the graph of the normal distribution with the binomial distribution, you can infer that as n increases, the binomial distribution becomes more like the normal distribution.

From the fixed assumptions one can assume that the champion team of the Brasileirão has approximately a 19.36% probability of winning 13 of 19 matches played at home. The probability of winning none is practically 0%. It can be noticed that the number of wins decreases after 13.

Supposing that the number of wins achieved by Palmeiras in the 2022 Brasileirão are enough for a team to become champion. For this, if the matches are independent of each other, this will only be possible if the team wins 13 of the 19 matches.

By the binomial $P(13 \leq X \leq 19)$, it has:

$$P(13 \leq X \leq 19) = \sum_{x=13}^{19} P(X = x).$$

Using Table 2, it can be calculated

$$P(13 \leq X \leq 19) = 0.94 + 0.176 + 0.125 + 0.0664 + 0.0249 + 0.00588 + 0.000657 = 0.59.$$

By the normal approximation of the binomial distribution with continuity correction, we have:

$$P(13 \leq X \leq 19) \approx P\left(13 - \frac{1}{2} \leq X \leq 19 + \frac{1}{2}\right) = P(12.5 \leq X \leq 19.5) \approx 3.86.$$

The hope and the variable are, respectively

$$E(X) = n \times p = 19 \times 0.68 = 12.92 \text{ and}$$

$$Var(X) = n \times p \times (1 - p) = 19 \times 0.68 \times 0.32 \approx 4.13$$

By employing the hope as the mean of the binomial and the variance as the normal distribution, still by the normal equation, one has: this equation is the normalized version of the gauss equation

$$P(13 \leq X \leq 19) \approx P\left(\frac{12.5 - 12.92}{\sqrt{4.13}} \leq \frac{X - 12.92}{\sqrt{4.13}} \leq \frac{19.5 - 12.92}{\sqrt{4.13}}\right) = \Phi(3.24) - \Phi(-0.206) = 0.581,$$

by which Phi is the normalized Gauss distribution. To find $P(14 \leq X \leq 19)$ using Poisson we have that $P(13 \leq X \leq 19) \approx P(X \geq 13)$. Considering data already obtained, $\alpha = 13$, X being a random variable, then

$$P(13 \leq X \leq 19) \approx P(X \geq 13) = \sum_{x=13}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\alpha} \alpha^x}{x!} \approx 0.54,$$

Using Bernoulli's distribution, the probability function is given by:

$$P(X = 0) = 0.68^0 \times 0.32 = 0.32,$$

$$P(X = 1) = 0.68 \times 0.32^0 = 0.68.$$

The results of the distribution confirm that the probability of winning or not winning a home game is 68% and 32% respectively.

9. Palmeiras Playing Away From Home

Let X be a random variable representing Palmeiras' number of away wins in n matches, with a constant

probability p . Ten of the 19 matches were won, so the probability of Palmeiras winning away from home is $p = 0.53$, and the probability of not winning (losses + draws) is $(1 - p) = 0.47$. As a result, the probability distribution for the independent variable X is binomial.

Table 3. Distribuição de probabilidade da variável aleatória $X \sim B(19; 0.53)$.

X	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$P(X=X)$	5.89^{-7}	1.26^{-5}	1.28^{-4}	8.18^{-4}	3.69^{-3}	0.0125	0.0328	0.0688	0.116	0.16
X	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
$P(X=X)$	0.181	0.167	0.125	0.076	0.0368	0.0138	3.89^{-4}	7.76^{-4}	9.72^{-5}	5.77^{-6}

Graph 3. Probability function graph of the random variable $X \sim B(19; 0.32)$.

Graph 4. Bell curve of Graph 1.

When Graphs 1 are compared 3, and 2 are compared 4, it is clear that the condition of playing at home has a significant influence on the outcome of the matches. According to graph 3, as the number of games won away from home decreases, the probability decreases. The expected value of the random variable X 's number of wins in $n = 19$ matches with constant probability $p = 0.68$ is:

$$E(x) = np = 19 \times 0.68 = 12.92$$

As already calculated, the variance of the number of home wins is 4.13. As for the variance in the number of away wins ($Var(Y)$):

$$Var(Y) = np = (1 - p) = 19 \times 0.53 \times 0.47 = 4.73$$

Thus, one can conclude from the variance that Palmeiras had more regularities at home than away from home.

10. Conclusion

Based on the data obtained from Palmeiras playing at home, it can be said that it performed better compared to its away games. Thus, answering the research question, it can be concluded that Palmeiras had plenty of advantages. Although the difference in probability is not extremely expressive, it is taken into consideration that some teams that played against Palmeiras are from São Paulo (i.e. a match of two teams in the same condition playing at home). An example is the São Paulo team that played against Palmeiras in São Paulo, which resulted in a draw. Thus, in terms of complete statistics, the analysis done is characterized as partially limited. Another limitation is the formulas chosen and used that do not have a proper global model, which may hinder the understanding of some individuals. For a better analysis, the possible impacts should be calculated in case two teams played at home in a game, extending the analysis to other factors that are not in focus in the work at hand such as the number of fans and the players on the field. In addition, more precise and globally popular formulas should be considered, since mathematics also considers itself as a language. Finally, to obtain more precise results, other teams from other states should be analyzed. Limitations

aside, this work should not be overlooked. Besides giving more credibility to soccer, the conduct of the exploration is also characterized as practical, helping students, those interested in soccer, and others see use in the application of mathematics.

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